

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CONFLICT ISSUES AND COPING STRATEGIES AMONG RURAL PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN SPECIAL POSITIONS A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF A RURAL PRESCHOOL SPECIAL POST TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Rural early childhood special education, as an integral part of grassroots early childhood education in the country, has made significant contributions to rural education. However, the issue of the loss of rural early childhood special post teachers (referred to as "rural post early childhood special group teachers") still remains unresolved. This article employs a qualitative analysis grounded in theory and utilizes interview methods to observe a rural preschool special post teacher (a rural preschool special group post teacher) for a semester. By searching and organizing relevant materials, truthfully restore the actual situation of the teacher's loss, and then analyze the reasons for the teacher's loss in combination with Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. Research has found that according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, the five types of conflicts that the teacher encounters in practice are the main reasons for loss: the conflict between "low income" and "high expenses", the conflict between "family responsibility" and "remote work", the conflict between "early career enthusiasm" and "later career burnout", the conflict between "rural contempt for early childhood education" and "national emphasis on early childhood education", The conflict between the "spiritual world needs" and the "lack of real life", and then propose relevant solutions.

Keywords: rural education; Early childhood education; Special position teachers; Teacher conflicts; Qualitative research.

Question raising

Currently, China is in a stage of rapid development in rural early childhood education. Both the "National Medium and Long Term Education Reform and Development Plan Outline (2010-2020)" and "China Education Modernization 2035" emphasize the need to prioritize rural early childhood education. With the gradual implementation of the three-year action plan for early childhood education in various regions, rural kindergartens are gradually increasing, and rural early childhood teachers are also gradually increasing with strong support from the state. Especially since 2006, the Ministry of Education, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, and the Central Organization Office have jointly launched and implemented the "Special Post Plan for School Teachers in Rural Compulsory Education Stage" [3], guiding and supporting outstanding graduates of preschool education to enter rural areas and achieve their educational dreams, greatly promoting rural preschool education work. However, in reality, many "rural preschool special position teachers" have chosen to resign in the near future after successfully joining the rural preschool education teacher team. Rural preschool special position teachers are a very important part of rural grassroots education. They, like the majority of rural teachers in primary and secondary schools, face many difficulties. Faced with a gradually growing industry group, representing and exploring the challenges it encounters in its existence, our research holds significant practical value and theoretical significance.

From September 2017 to January 2020, the author worked at a rural grassroots kindergarten for three years

to gain a deep understanding of the work and current situation of rural kindergarten teachers, and had deep feelings for rural preschool special position teachers. Through observation and interviews throughout the entire semester from September 2020 to January 2021, the author has acquired a wealth of first-hand information and will truthfully restore the reality of the loss of preschool special position teachers. Using the "Maslow hierarchy of needs theory", the author analyzes the current situation of the loss of preschool special position teachers and proposes the five major conflicts encountered by preschool teachers in practice, providing factual support for relevant theoretical research. To comply with research ethics, the author has removed the name of the kindergarten and replaced it with A kindergarten.

Research methods and objects

This study uses a qualitative research method based on grounded theory, mainly using unstructured interview method to collect data. The researcher did not find a ready-made interview outline, but independently designed an interview framework suitable for this study based on the research purpose and referring to existing research literature. The interview outline includes basic personal information, family background information, the entire process from employment to resignation, the reasons that affect resignation, opinions on reducing teacher turnover, and supplementary information of the respondents. The researchers conducted formal and informal interviews on the samples, with each interview lasting 20-30 minutes. The entire interview process was recorded and recorded in written form. Finally, the

main reasons for teacher turnover were analyzed using Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory.

A Kindergarten is located in a remote rural area of Wudu District, Longnan City, Gansu Province, 35 kilometers away from the town. In May 2008, according to the requirements of the higher authorities, the school was divided into two schools: junior high school and primary school. In 2010, the kindergarten was included in the primary school and became an affiliated kindergarten of the rural central primary school. In the autumn semester of 2020, there were 175 preschool children in the kindergarten, with three classes: primary, secondary, and primary. There were a total of 8 faculty members, including 6 full-time teachers, with a teacher to child ratio of 1:29. This is a significant difference from the 1:7-1:9 ratio between full-time kindergarten caregivers and young children stipulated in the latest "Kindergarten Staff Allocation Standards (Provisional)" issued by the Ministry of Education on January 8, 2013. The teacher to child ratio is too large, which is a common problem in rural kindergartens. All 8 teachers are female, with an imbalance in gender ratio. 3 people major in preschool education, 1 person major in music education, 2 people major in primary education, and the remaining 2 people are temporary employees without relevant disciplinary backgrounds. Due to the fact that all 6 teachers are currently employed and their homes are in other cities or cities, they have no intention of settling down in the school dormitory, while the other 2 are local residents living at home. We can see that there is a very shortage of professional teachers in the kindergarten, with a significant disparity in the proportion of teachers to children. This is the main problem faced by rural kindergartens in China. This is mainly due to the fact that rural kindergartens are mostly affiliated with primary school management, and most of them adopt methods such as transferring primary school teachers and hiring teachers to meet basic needs. It is not surprising that there are various problems with special early childhood teachers when there is a serious shortage of professional teachers.

The purpose of selecting research subjects is to explore the reasons for the loss of specialized preschool teachers through the grounded theory of qualitative research methods, and then propose relevant solutions. In order to better complete this study, a 28 year old female teacher in a special position for preschool education was selected as the research object using purposive sampling method based on the principle of convenience and effectiveness. Due to the fact that the researchers witnessed the entire process of the teacher's employment and resignation, their observation and recording were more comprehensive. To follow ethical principles, this study will use "L teacher" to refer to the research subjects.

Research results and analysis

Through interviews and exchanges with Teacher L, we have come to the conclusion that there are five reasons why she ultimately fled the rural special post preschool education team: economic, family, occupational pressure, environmental, practical and spiritual needs are asymmetrical, and she feels unable to work and live in rural kindergartens for a long time. In terms

of economy, as I have just started my job, my current work status is a "three-year probationary period", with only 3183 yuan allocated by the government every month. Within three years, I also paid 775 yuan for the five insurances and one fund through personal contributions, with an actual salary of 2408 yuan. There is almost no remaining weekly car fare and daily expenses for returning home; In terms of family, her boyfriend and she often have conflicts due to long-distance issues, and in addition, both parents have reached the marriageable age and also hope to end their single status as soon as possible; In terms of occupational pressure, due to the long-term lack of teachers in rural kindergartens and the continuous expansion of the number of young children, she felt that the pressure was quite high and completely inconsistent with her imagined preschool education work; In terms of environment, although Teacher L is a rural child, due to her long-term residence in the city during her university years, she has become accustomed to urban life, and everything in the countryside makes her feel inconvenient and unfamiliar; In terms of practical and spiritual needs, it goes without saying that rural areas are located in remote areas, and the needs in reality cannot be met, and spiritual needs cannot be guaranteed. Due to various reasons, they began to pay attention to the opportunities for urban recruitment. When the new round of recruitment exams began, they immediately registered and after several months of working and studying, they finally entered the interview as they wished. Although they were detained by the local unit and the education bureau during their resignation period, due to their determination, they resolutely resigned to obtain the urban recruitment.

Based on the above case analysis, the researcher will apply the "Maslow hierarchy of needs theory" to analyze the reasons why L teacher left rural kindergartens. Maslow (1943) pointed out that people need motivation to achieve certain needs, and some needs take precedence over others. Maslow's hierarchy of needs is a motivational theory in psychology, including a five level model of human needs, typically depicted as levels within a pyramid. From the bottom up of the hierarchy, the needs are: physiological (food and clothing), safety (job security), social needs (friendship), respect, and self actualization. This five stage model can be divided into insufficient demand and increasing demand. The first four levels are usually referred to as defect requirements (D requirements), while the highest level is called growth requirements (B requirements). Due to long-term inability to meet the five major human needs, especially young graduates who are forced to join the ranks of special post teachers due to their poor family background, the "special post teachers for young children" in educational practice are unable to meet their daily needs due to economic income, the huge contrast between rural living conditions and university life, the inability to socialize normally, and the lack of respect for early childhood education in rural areas, It has been constantly impacted by real life. This article will explain from the perspective of five major conflicts, to explain why "preschool special duty teachers" would flee the rural teaching team.

The Conflict between "Low Income" and "High Expenditure

Salary is the first requirement for entering the workplace. For rural students with difficult economic conditions, it is already a dream for them to obtain a job with staffing, economic stability, and high social status after graduation. Rooted in traditional Chinese thinking, special post preschool teachers are also a part of the "iron rice bowl", and they, like civil servants and public institutions, enjoy the welfare benefits of the state. Both in terms of economy and social status, they have been given a good future. But only after joining the workforce did we realize that the conflict between "low income" and "high expenses" is happening every day. The first three years of rural preschool special position teachers are "probationary periods", and their salaries often only meet the basic needs of food and accommodation. The research subject L teacher is a rural child, with the school 35 kilometers away from the town and the town 85 kilometers away from home. The first economic expenditure we face is transportation costs; Eating in the school cafeteria every day, although the cost of eating is not high, it is also an expense; Provide financial assistance to parents and younger brothers every month to reduce the burden on the family; Finally, it is necessary to socialize with your boyfriend and friends normally during the Chinese New Year holiday. From the above information, it can be seen that increasing economic expenses due to transportation factors, daily food and transportation, and normal communication are major issues that L teachers face. L teachers earn over 2000 yuan per month, which is not much except for normal expenses. They even occasionally need to swipe credit cards to maintain their daily lives.

Newly hired teachers, due to their limited financial resources and no other income, are constantly affected by the conflict between "low income" and "high expenses", which is one of the key reasons why "preschool special duty teachers" choose to flee the rural teaching team in the later stage.

The Conflict between 'Family Responsibility' and 'Remote Work'

Family responsibility is one of the fundamental issues faced by every adult. Preschool special duty teachers do not get married or have no boyfriend when they first enter the workplace, and teachers with boyfriends also face the need for stable work and thus want stable marriage. Teacher L and her boyfriend have been in love for three years. In rural areas, parents with backward thinking often hope to get married immediately after stable work. Boyfriends also want to end their unstable relationship because they have been away for a long time. However, due to the remote location of Teacher L's workplace, it is inconvenient to meet them, and the romantic relationship has become increasingly unstable. Over the years, her boyfriend's complaints have increased, and she has become increasingly suspicious of their relationship. In a certain context, being admitted as a special preschool teacher can actually lead to unstable romantic relationships. Teacher L's situation is like this, let alone other married and pregnant teachers. Preschool special duty teachers have always

been unable to balance their "family responsibilities" and "remote work".

Through research on Teacher L, this is also one of the factors that "special duty preschool teachers" choose to leave the rural teaching team, especially for female teachers who have just entered the workplace and are located in a remote area and cannot further complete their marital relationship with their boyfriends, the situation is even more complex.

The Conflict between "Early Career Enthusiasm" and "Later Career Burnout"

Burnout refers to the state of physical and mental fatigue and exhaustion that individuals experience under the pressure of work. Originally proposed by Freudenberger in 1974, Freudenberger believed that job burnout is a symptom of emotional exhaustion that is most likely to occur in the helping industry. Subsequently, Maslach et al. referred to the psychological syndrome of responding to long-term emotional and interpersonal stressors at work as occupational burnout. It is generally believed that occupational burnout is an extreme reaction when an individual is unable to cope with work pressure smoothly, and it is a state of emotional, attitudinal, and behavioral exhaustion that accompanies long-term stress experiences. The teaching profession is a typical 'helping industry', especially in rural areas where children are mostly left behind without parents. Sometimes, teachers not only take on the responsibility of education, but also require more care like 'mothers'. The first three years of the "Preschool Special Post Teacher" period were a period of professional enthusiasm. During this period, teachers had a passion for rural education, a love for children, and a vision for a better future in rural education, and invested a huge amount of work enthusiasm. However, returning to the reality of rural education, "preschool special position teachers" have transformed from initial "professional enthusiasm" to "professional fatigue" three years later. Just like the L teacher we investigated, firstly, the class size and number of teachers in rural kindergartens and urban kindergartens are different. In the past, an internship class was composed of two preschool teachers and one caregiver, fully meeting the policy requirement of "two teachers and one guarantee". The number of class children sizes in a class is fixed, and the number of students in both small and large classes will not exceed 35. However, due to a serious shortage of teachers in rural kindergartens, there is only one or two teachers in a class, and it is even more difficult to talk about caregivers. Even if teachers take on their own job, they also need to take on the responsibility of caregivers, which often results in a large workload. Not to mention the class size, Teacher L's small class can sometimes reach around 60 people, and the teacher's work is unbearable, making it difficult to carry out teaching activities normally.

The severe shortage of teachers and the rapid expansion of class sizes have gradually led to a sense of professional fatigue among preschool teachers in rural areas, and the conflict between the two is also one of the reasons for teacher turnover.

The Conflict between "Rural Disdain for Early Childhood Education" and "National Emphasis on Early Childhood Education"

Preschool education is currently not included in nine-year compulsory education and is only being piloted at a few points. As it has not yet been included in compulsory education, although the government has some subsidies, parents still need to bear a portion of it themselves. For rural areas, this is also a significant investment. Some parents neglect early childhood education in order to reduce family expenses and wait until the age of compulsory education to attach importance to their children's education. Against the backdrop of the country's emphasis on early childhood education, there is a significant gap between rural early childhood education and national requirements. The neglect of early childhood education in rural areas has also disappointed many preschool teachers. Teacher L leads a small class with 55 students, almost 80% of whom are left behind children. The children are under the care of grandparents or other elders. The backwardness of rural education concepts makes them feel that early childhood education is actually the precursor of primary education, and parents do not care what interesting things their children learn in kindergarten. Just blindly asking the teacher, "What is the Pinyin you learned today? Did the kindergarten teach you numbers? Why didn't you have homework tonight? Why don't you go to kindergarten without teaching anything?" This is completely inconsistent with Teacher L's acceptance of "prohibiting elementary education". In addition, many children in rural kindergartens do not have parents around them, making it extremely difficult to engage in home or parent-child activities. Even if many activities are carefully prepared for the children, the attitude of parents is still unclear.

The consistent lack of emphasis on early childhood education by rural parents and the love of early childhood teachers for early childhood education form a strong contrast. The conflict between these two aspects has made "preschool special duty teachers" doubt whether their major is useful, and holding such a skeptical attitude is also one of the factors that keep some preschool teachers leaving the teaching team.

The Conflict between "Spiritual World Needs" and "Lack of Real Life"

Spiritual needs refer to the needs that satisfy people's psychology and spiritual activities, including their spiritual desires and pursuits, such as self-esteem, unleashing their potential, and spiritual entertainment. Compared to material needs, spiritual needs are higher-level needs. In the concept of spiritual needs proposed by Walker Hobb, it is emphasized that true spiritual needs should be a new and more valuable currency of life, reflected in abundance, happiness, satisfaction, health and happiness. We should have a life and work that matches our values, as well as a vibrant social circle that can provide support for us. We know that a person's true needs include material conditions and spiritual civilization. The spiritual needs of "preschool special position teachers" also require special attention from us. When personal economic income cannot meet

their own needs, the satisfaction of spiritual needs becomes precious and the only hope for supporting their career. However, reality often gives "preschool special position teachers" a head-on blow. Although Teacher L is a rural student, her university is located in developed areas of first tier cities. After entering university, the rich and colorful university entertainment activities, diverse club activities, and having a group of like-minded classmates have greatly improved her spiritual life compared to before. But when I was admitted to the countryside, I realized that there was no entertainment equipment available. My daily life consisted of attending classes and watching TV or preparing for classes in the dormitory, and my spiritual needs were not fully met.

From this, we can also see that there is a significant difference between the spiritual needs of "preschool special position teachers" and their actual life. For teachers who have lived in university city life for four years and have graduated and devoted themselves to urban preschool education, there is no difference. The lack of spiritual needs also makes it impossible to work specifically.

Through the above research and the combination of Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, we can see that D needs cannot be met, whether it is physiological, safety, social needs, respect, etc., and B needs cannot be self fulfilled. It is normal for L teachers to have better opportunities to take other career positions and leave the village.

Reflection and suggestions

At the 12th meeting of the Standing Committee of the 13th National People's Congress held on August 22, 2019, Minister of Education Chen Baosheng proposed in the "Report of the State Council on the Reform and Development of Preschool Education" that there are insufficient resources for preschool education in rural areas, ethnic minority areas, and concentrated and contiguous poverty-stricken areas, and efforts will be made to fill these shortcomings. According to the content of the document, it is necessary to promote the overall development and quality improvement of preschool education in each township by implementing rural revitalization and promoting the operation of each public kindergarten; Improve the layout of rural kindergartens to meet the entry needs of rural areas; The central and local finance arranges special funds to support preschool education, with a focus on rural and impoverished areas, and increases support for rural preschool education; Encourage localities with conditions to pilot the implementation of living subsidy policies for rural public kindergarten teachers, and further stabilize the teaching staff of rural kindergartens. Revitalizing rural preschool education and stabilizing the rural special post preschool teacher team not only requires strong support from the state and government, but also requires local support from rural areas and the transformation of teachers' thoughts. Only by connecting the three can the "five major conflicts" of the rural special post preschool teacher team be resolved.

Change personal attitudes and reduce self expenditure

Emerging media refers to new media software such as Tiktok, Kwai, Weibo, official account, etc. It is known that new media have a great impact on life and work, making it easy for many rural children to see the outside world and learn different knowledge by relying on the Internet, and also making children in big cities pay attention to children who live very different lives in the same world even in a superior environment. As a new way of life, new media not only brings challenges but also opportunities for rural special duty teachers.

The short films taken by rural special post teachers, such as "Xiehhaha No Teacher" and "Guangxi Hechi Online Red Teacher", on platforms such as Tiktok, have caused great repercussions and good traffic. For example, "Xiehhaha No Teacher" shows us a new perspective by taking advantage of her rural teacher's identity. She starts from 5:30 in the morning to record her day as a teacher, She shared her daily life with the left behind children in rural areas and a completely different side from urban life. In her video, you can see the children's dark faces and innocent smiles, as well as the harsh environment and persistent efforts. We were even more surprised to find that the "rural special duty teachers" who were originally located in remote areas have their own topic and traffic characteristics, The maximum video playback volume of 'Hexi Haha No Teacher' has reached millions, and the likes rate is even higher than 580000. From this, we can see that in the new era of "traffic is king", rural special post preschool teachers can also create their own "traffic age" like the "online celebrity" on Tiktok by making rational use of local resources and local topics, and ingenious video publicity of rural teachers, Firstly, it has promoted the characteristics of local rural areas and made more people aware of the hard work and hardships of special post teachers. Secondly, it has also increased one's own income, and even this income will bring more substantial income than their own job, which to some extent alleviates the problem of low income for rural preschool special post teachers.

And in recent years, the Chinese government has strongly supported early childhood education and new media undertakings, and the country has also been continuously introducing more incentive policies. Although the importance of early childhood education is still not as high as that of primary school teachers and other education, especially in remote rural areas where low wages and treatment have caused many teachers to have misconceptions. The current reward and punishment system in rural kindergartens also makes teachers complain, rural special post early childhood teachers should start from reality, Keep up with the trend of the times, seize rural traffic, create a unique era of traffic, and explore new ways to receive different salary rewards.

Add unit activities to balance family and career

The family is always the most powerful reserve force for staff, especially for preschool teachers who are deeply involved in rural education. The moment of returning home every week is the most relaxing time, allowing them to enjoy the joy of family and the

warmth of the family. However, through research, we also found that "preschool special duty teachers" are unable to take into account family responsibilities and accompany children's growth for a long time, The increasing number of unstable factors in families has led to teachers being unable to work in rural areas for a long time.

In fact, many rural kindergartens have unique natural environments and unit characteristics. Kindergarten leaders can add unit activities on this basis to close the relationship between husband, wife, and children. For example, they can rent a bus to bring their husbands and children who cannot meet together on weekends, and the cafeteria of the unit can also let everyone eat together and cherish the hard-earned parent-child time on weekends. Alternatively, during holidays, it is also possible to have husbands and children participate in team building activities at the workplace, which not only brings the staff closer to each other, but also takes advantage of this opportunity to allow preschool teachers to meet the families of children who have not seen each other for a long time.

Balancing work and life pressure at the same time is an ability that a qualified preschool teacher should possess. On the one hand, it is necessary to achieve cognitive debugging, have a strong willingness to run a happy and harmonious family, not bring the frustrations and difficulties in work into daily families, change the concept of no distinction between work and family, and be good at managing the family while completing work. On the other hand, it is also necessary to achieve behavioral adjustment and relieve work pressure. As many rural special post preschool teachers who have both family life and rural work, the pressure of life is immense no matter what difficulties you face. Therefore, as a qualified preschool special post teacher, self balancing family life is also an essential skill.

Reduce job burnout and establish a sense of loyalty

Loyalty itself is a rational behavior, guiding the teacher community to establish a sense of loyalty can reduce the possibility of quitting the teaching industry, and can also expand the enthusiasm period of preschool teachers for their profession. Rural kindergartens are currently in the early stages of comprehensive promotion and are not mandatory requirements for compulsory education. Although the country is vigorously promoting it, it is difficult to pay off historical debts, which has become a weakness and weak link in the education field. Therefore, establishing the loyalty of preschool special position teachers to the kindergarten organization during this period can greatly protect preschool teachers from loss.

Improving the organizational loyalty of preschool special duty teachers can be divided into two aspects: on the one hand, kindergartens help teachers establish loyalty concepts, and on the other hand, kindergartens support informal organizations to cultivate teacher loyalty. The first aspect is that kindergartens help teachers establish a sense of loyalty. From the beginning of their employment, kindergartens help young teachers to uphold their loyalty to the organization and kindergarten,

and cultivate their loyalty through various negative aspects such as life, activities, and dietary habits. The second aspect of supporting informal organizations in cultivating teacher loyalty refers to the fact that the establishment of loyalty concepts not only relies on the organization of the kindergarten itself, but also must play the role of informal organizations. Informal organizations arise within formal organizations and are a loose, informal group formed naturally by people in the process of working together, based on emotions such as emotions and hobbies. Informal groups within the teacher community are common, formed based on common interests, majors, backgrounds, and units. Informal groups can provide teachers with needs that kindergartens cannot meet, creating a sense of dependence and belonging for preschool teachers towards informal organizations, thereby establishing loyalty to their own unit and organization. This is to some extent beneficial for preschool teachers' loyalty to the organization.

Rural kindergarten teachers dedicate their youngest and most beautiful years to the countryside and provide the warmest side to their children. However, due to the rapid loss of professional enthusiasm and lack of organizational loyalty, kindergarten teachers gradually lose the confidence to persevere. In the long run, the attractiveness has decreased, the passion for work has subsided, and the teaching level has decreased, which is extremely detrimental to the healthy development of kindergartens. Establish a loyalty system that is fully applicable to special professions in early childhood education, allowing teachers who aspire to engage in early childhood education to engage in early childhood education for a lifetime, and giving them a full sense of achievement and honor.

Adopting new forms of publicity to create respect for teachers and children

Early childhood education is the initial stage of education, which has a significant impact on the formation of children's outlook on life, values, and worldview. The efforts of early childhood teachers cannot be reflected in academic performance in a timely manner like in primary and secondary schools. However, early childhood is the most important and initial stage of a person's life, and the lack of early childhood education can affect children's lifelong growth. We need to widely promote the importance of early childhood education, so that rural parents can firmly establish a childhood that allows their children to have enough food and clothing, as well as a childhood that receives enlightenment education and correct guidance. We need to encourage rural parents to change their indifferent attitude towards preschool education, and encourage interaction between school preschool teacher education and parents' attention, forming a new model for jointly promoting the healthy development of preschool education.

And the new model of promoting the healthy development of preschool education can also be shifted from traditional promotion models to new ones. In traditional promotion models, kindergartens are simply left to fight alone and establish regular lectures and promotional activities. Often, many rural parents leave halfway through the activities because experts and

teachers are too rigid to arouse the interest and resonance of rural parents, Spent a lot of time and energy but could not achieve the expected results. We can adopt a new publicity model to make rural parents unconsciously follow the footsteps of teachers, and observe that both rural and urban parents cannot do without the influence of the internet. The internet, as an essential thing in modern society, is also influencing everyone's values and educational views. Rural kindergartens can, with the help of the Education Bureau and the local integrated media center, create a video about "how to establish a correct view of children". Many new media software has positioning functions, and when rural parents locate themselves locally, they can automatically play this type of video. Rural parents will also achieve the expected results due to subtle influence.

Under the standardized guidance of kindergartens and integrated media centers, rural parents should attach equal importance to early childhood education as urban parents, enhance their respect for preschool teachers, and attach importance to early childhood education.

Improve rural mechanisms and utilize spare time

Rural kindergartens located in remote areas cannot have the same real-life conditions as urban kindergartens, and their extracurricular life is dull and monotonous. Their expectations for the spiritual world cannot be met, and the pressure in their work cannot be released in a timely manner. The effectiveness of their work often fails to meet practical requirements, and even if their real-life conditions are not met, their spiritual world cannot be satisfied.

How to balance the spiritual world and the real world is a problem that relevant education departments and kindergartens need to pay special attention to. In fact, rural areas are rich in resources, and different rural areas have different natural resources. How to make good use of these natural resources to achieve a balance between the spiritual world and the real world is a problem that we need to think about. After learning about different rural natural resources, it was discovered that Southern Kindergarten organized many interesting "rural water town activities" to balance the spiritual world of teachers, such as duck catching competitions, lotus seed picking activities, and organizing female teachers to walk in Hanfu and take photos in Jiangnan water town. These activities greatly comforted rural special duty teachers. There are Jiangnan water towns in the south and the Loess Plateau in the north. By making good use of local characteristics, we can also carry out interesting activity plans, giving preschool special teachers abundant free time, in order to achieve a balance between the spiritual world and the real world.

Organizing leisure activities suitable for the local area, enriching their extracurricular life, reducing their work and life pressure, and meeting their spiritual needs are issues that every rural kindergarten and relevant education department needs to pay attention to. Balancing the real life and spiritual life of rural special post preschool teachers is the key to reducing the loss of rural preschool teachers.

Epilogue

Rural education is the most basic education at the grassroots level in China, and early childhood education is also the initial education in education. Rural early childhood education is related to tens of thousands of rural families, and rural special post teachers, as the link between education and family, connect the future of every rural student. The issue of the loss of specialized preschool teachers seriously affects the future development of students and rural education, and this problem needs to be properly addressed. Currently, establishing a stable team of rural preschool education teachers is the primary task of running rural grassroots education well. Based on the "Maslow hierarchy of needs theory" factors, rural preschool special position teachers are mainly due to low economic efficiency, imbalanced families, unsatisfied professional enthusiasm, insufficient emphasis on preschool education in rural areas, and the inability to meet expectations of spiritual reality, leading to the loss of the teaching team. Further measures need to be taken by the country and local authorities to attract outstanding talents and maintain the stability of local preschool education teacher resources in order to expand rural early childhood education, gradually forming a situation of "being able to go down", "being able to stay", and "being able to teach well", in order to achieve the revitalization of rural early childhood education.

References

1. Outline of the National Medium and Long Term Education Reform and Development Plan (2010-2020) [EB/OL] (2010 07 29) [2020 04 02] http://www.moe.gov.cn/srcsite/A01/s7048/201007/t20100729_171904.html
2. The Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council issued the "2035 Modernization of Education in China" [EB/OL] (February 23, 2019) [April 2, 2020] http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/2019-02/23/content_5367987.htm
3. Special Post Plan for School Teachers in Rural Compulsory Education Stage [EB/OL] (2006-05-15) http://www.gov.cn/ztl/ysbgjd/content_551036.htm
4. Standard for Staffing of Kindergarten Teachers (Provisional) [EB/OL] (2013-01-01) http://www.gov.cn/zwgk/2013-01/23/content_2318295.htm
5. Yuan Zhenzhen. Analysis of the Reasons for the Loss of Rural Primary School Teachers in the Process of Urbanization - A Narrative Study on the Loss of a Rural Primary School Teacher [J]. Education Observation, 2020, (6)
6. Ning Zhuzhu. Analysis of Rural Kindergarten Teacher Team Construction and Stability Measures from the Perspective of Psychological Contract [J]. Enterprise and Management 2020, (9)
7. Kong Lu, Li Shifang. Qualitative analysis of the loss of private preschool teachers in rural areas [J]. Changsha University Journal, 2021, (1)
8. Zhu Xiuhong, Liu Ronghuai. A Study on the Mobility Willingness and Stability Policy of Rural Youth: An Analysis Perspective Based on the Theory of Individual Environment Matching [J]. Education Development Research, 2019 (2)
9. Liu Min, Shi Yabing. Analysis of the Motivation Mechanism of Rural Teacher Loss and the Training of Rural Teachers with Local Emotions: A Study Based on the Life History of "Special Post Teachers" in the 1980s [J]. Contemporary Education Science, 2016, (6)
10. Wang Yanling, Li Huiqin. Empirical Analysis of Rural Teacher Mobility and Turnover Intention [J]. Education Sciences, 2017, (3)
11. Xi Meihong. On the Rationality of Rural Teacher Turnover: A Theoretical Perspective Based on Equity [J]. Theoretical Review, 2016, (2)
12. Long Xianzhong, Zhou Jing, Dong Shujun. Governance of Teacher Turnover in Universities: Based on the Theory of "Exit Appeal Loyalty", Higher Education Research, 2014, (6)